

The Healthy Ramadan Campaign 2019

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Bismah Ali BSc Occupational Therapy at London Southbank University and Member of BIMA Ramadan Campaign

Background: In light of the significant attention drawn to the role of Health Promotion by Public Health England's Strategy (published 2019), British Islamic Medical Association (BIMA) has successfully been running campaigns to encourage healthy eating and maintaining health during Ramadan. This is the 3rd year we have done this campaign.

Method: The team has developed Power point Presentations involving a range of medical professionals such as GPs, Consultants, Diabetologists, Dieticians and other allied health professionals. The project aims to increase awareness of healthy eating, maintaining health and wellbeing during Ramadan, manage drug intakes and address issues surrounding medical conditions. The resources have been informed by research from Diabetes UK, International Glaucoma Association and supported by Muslim Council of Britain.

Results: In 2019, 55 mosques and 11 radio stations across the UK have participated in teaching the local community about leading a Healthy Ramadan despite chronic illnesses such as Diabetes. This involved approximately 80 people who have been from a range of healthcare professionals delivering a talk explaining the importance of maintaining good health in Ramadan from a medical perspective and reducing the risk of potential health complications. Professionals have encouraged their local communities, for example the South Asian to visit their GPs and discuss the risks of fasting due to the prevalence of cholesterol-related and diabetes-related diseases.

Although there were no feedback forms filled attendees to the presentation gave very positive feedback about the talk and asked pertinent questions about their health.

Conclusion: We have shown that there is an appetite in the community to improve their over health and to fast during Ramadan safely keeping in line with the principles of their belief. For 2020, the team envisage that the project will expand to many more Mosques, as more professionals from different regions in the UK come onboard with the project.